

POLYPROPYLENE SUTURE VERSUS ABSORBABLE TACK MESH FIXATION IN LAPAROSCOPIC PECTOPEXY: A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT Background: The aim of this study to investigate whether tacker and suture materials used for mesh fixation in the laparoscopic pectopexy would yield significant differences concerning feasibility, safety, and postoperative outcomes. **Methods:** A total of 26 women who underwent laparoscopic pectopexy between January 2015 and June 2017 at the Kocaeli Derince Education and Research Hospital were retrospectively analyzed. Fourteen patients had the mesh fixation onto the iliopectineal ligaments, and vaginal stump with polypropylene suture using intra-corporeal suturing technique and twelve patients had the mesh fixation tacks via the absorbable mesh fixation devices of commercial tack device - Absorbatack™. (Suture group: 14 subjects, tacker group: 12 subjects). **Results:** Twenty-six patients underwent laparoscopic pectopexy. Tacker group had a significantly shorter duration of operation and time required for placement of mesh than the suture group ($P<0.001$). The Visual Pain Scale (VAS) score rates at the 6th, 12th, 24th hours did not demonstrate significant differences between the two groups. ($P=0.159$, $P=0.222$, $P=0.215$, respectively). The follow-up period in the suture group averaged 16.4 ± 7.3 months and 13.8 ± 4.7 months in the tacker group ($P=0.312$). **Conclusion:** Fixation of mesh onto the iliopectineal ligament and vaginal vault via absorbable mesh fixation devices may be a safe, feasible, and time-saving procedure that might be an alternative to polypropylene suture fixation. However, this study displays the initial experiences of "absorbable mesh fixation device" usage in laparoscopic pectopexy. Further prospective comparative studies are necessary to show long term results.

KEYWORDS Laparoscopic prolapse surgery; pectopexy; surgical fixation devices; surgical mesh; vaginal prolapse

Introduction

Pelvic organ prolapse [POP] is a common disorder resulting herniation of the pelvic organs through the vaginal walls in women. Women have an 11–19% risk of undergoing surgery for

POP or incontinence [1].

The POP risk factors include age, sexual activity, history of vaginal delivery, previous prolapse surgery, previous urinary incontinence surgery and hysterectomy history, especially when performed for a prolapse [2]. Due to the high hysterectomy rate, the incidence of vaginal vault repair after a hysterectomy is 3.6 per 1,000 women/year [3], and this ratio increases with advancing age [4]. There may be a relationship between POP and hysterectomy that is not well elucidated. Patients with POP may complain of urinary dysfunction (irritative symptoms, obstructed voiding, urinary incontinence), defecation dysfunction (outlet obstruction, faecal urgency or incontinence) and symptoms associated with a vaginal protrusion (sexual dysfunction, vaginal pressure, lower back pain, dyspareunia). Unfortunately,

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these symptoms have a negative effect on the quality of life [5].

Adequate support for the vaginal cuff is the essential part of the POP surgery. Anterior (cystocele) and posterior (rectocele, enterocele) compartment defect repairs may fail unless the vaginal cuff is sufficiently supported [6]. There are many different surgical treatments for apical vaginal prolapse. A laparoscopic sacrocolpopexy is considered to be the gold standard in surgical procedures for apical vaginal defect repairs, the laparoscopic pectopexy technique described as a new alternative surgical procedure in 2010, especially for obese women [7]. A laparoscopic pectopexy is a surgical option in which a mesh-fixation at the iliopectineal ligament and the vaginal vault. In this procedure, the mesh follows the natural anatomical structures (round and broad ligaments) to maintain the physiological axis, and it eventually fixes the weakness and vaginal vault prolapse using the lateral parts of the iliopectineal ligaments on both sides. In a randomized trial on 85 patients, Noe et al. presented that the pectopexy offers clear, practical advantages compared with laparoscopic sacropexy and this procedure is at least equivalent to the sacral colpopexy in respect to the relapse rate of apical descensus. A laparoscopic pectopexy is regarded as a minimally invasive procedure with a low risk of complications, which provides a safe operating field due to the far distances of the ureter, bowels and vessels. The iliopectineal ligament is a strong structure and holds suture well [8]. Furthermore, it provides adequate material for mesh fixation [9].

Studies comparing the efficacy and postoperative results of the different suture techniques for mesh fixation to the iliopectineal ligament are limited in the medical literature. However, Sauerwald et al. [10] reported that there were no significant differences in the stiffness and failure modes between continuous sutures and a simplified single interrupted suture technique.

An absorbable mesh fixation device has not yet been adopted for fixation of mesh in the iliopectineal ligament in a laparoscopic pectopexy. Nevertheless, it has been accepted for laparoscopic hernia repair in the field of general surgery due to its potential advantages, such as a shortened mesh placement time [11,12] without an increase in the hernia recurrence rate. However, the effects of a mechanical tacking device on the postoperative pain score and chronic pain are controversial [11-13]. Given the advantages, absorbable mesh fixation devices should be considered in gynaecology, where it is conceivable to fix the mesh to a strong iliopectineal ligament in the pelvis.

The mesh fixation onto the iliopectineal ligament with a suture material can sometimes be frustrating and time-consuming during the process. We postulated that mesh fixation onto the iliopectineal ligament, and vaginal cuff via an absorbable device may be an excellent alternative to the mesh fixation with polypropylene suture materials. In this retrospective study, we aimed to investigate whether tacker and polypropylene suture techniques regarding the mesh placement time, operation time, pain scores at 6, 12 and 24 hours, total analgesic requirements, and early and late postoperative complications.

Materials and Methods

A total of 26 women who underwent laparoscopic pectopexies by a single surgeon (Ahmet Kale) between January 2015 and June 2017 at Kocaeli Derince Education and Research Hospital in Turkey were included in this retrospective study. In this retrospective study, 14 patients (suture group) had mesh fixations with polypropylene sutures using an intracorporeal suturing

Table 1 Patients characteristics, preoperative POP-Q measurements and intraoperative results and complications

Parameters	Tacker group (n=12) Mean (\pm SD)	Suture group (n=14) Mean (\pm SD)	P value
Age(yrs)	59.3 \pm 7.0	59.7 \pm 9.1	0.900
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.2 \pm 2.7	27.6 \pm 2.0	0.52
Gravida	2.8 \pm 0.7	5.3 \pm 2.6	
Parity	2.6 \pm 0.7	4.1 \pm 2.0	
Type of delivery (number, %)			
Caesarean section	1 (8.3%)	2(14.3 %)	
Vaginal delivery	11(91.7 %)	12(85.7 %)	
Stage of prolapse (number, %) (According to POP-Q classification)			
StageII	1 (8.3%)	2(14.3 %)	
StageIII	1 (8.3%)	2(14.3 %)	
StageIV	7(58.4 %)	8(57.1 %)	
Average placement of mesh time (min.)	16.6 \pm 3.7	34.3 \pm 5.9	<0.001*
Hgb drop level (mg/dl)	0.9 \pm 0.7	0.9 \pm 0.6	0.979**
Intraoperative complications (number of patients)			
Bladder injury	0	1	-
Bowel injury	0	0	-
Vessel injury	0	0	-
BMI: body mass index SD: standard deviation Hgb: haemoglobin			

technique, and 12 patients (tacker group) had the mesh fixations with the AbsorbaTack™ absorbable mesh fixation device (Covidien Corp., Mansfield, MA, USA). All patients' data were collected from the hospital database, and the surgical video records and clinical outcomes were analyzed. The pain was quantified using the 10 cm Visual Analog Scale [VAS]. The vaginal protrusion was assessed by physical examination and ultrasound imaging. The Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification [POP-Q] system was used to define the vaginal prolapse level. The patients who underwent laparoscopic pectopexies with symptomatic vaginal apical prolapses [POP-Q stage \geq II] were eligible for inclusion [14-15]. The exclusion criterion was a previous vaginal prolapse correction operation. The patients were asked to provide a number from 0 to 10 on the scale to rate the pain intensity, in the postoperative period. (0=no pain, 10=worst pain) [16].

We documented age, body mass index [BMI, kg/m²], history of previous delivery, history of previous urogynecology surgery, preoperative history of incontinence, vaginal prolapse stage, total operation time, mesh placement time, type of suture material, intraoperative complications (injuries to the bladder, bowels and vessels), postoperative serum hemoglobin drop (difference

between preoperative and postoperative, 24-hour interval), postoperative pain at 6, 12 and 24 hours (VAS score), postoperative total analgesic requirements and average hospital stay. At least 6 months after the operation, the following data was obtained: follow-up time, vaginal prolapse recurrence, voiding difficulties, dyspareunia and lower back pain. The mesh placement time was identified as the average time between the placement of the mesh in the abdominal cavity and completion of the fixation.

All patients gave informed written consent for the use of their operation videos and images. This study was approved by the ethical committee of the Kocaeli University (registration number KÜ GOKAEK 2018/1.11.2018/3). All procedures were conducted by the approved guidelines which also confirmed to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

Surgical procedures

For this surgical Procedure, a standard rigid 30°, 10-mm laparoscope, an insufflator, trocars, 5-mm laparoscopic instruments, 5-mm grasping forceps, a Harmonic scalpel (Ethicon, Cincinnati, OH, USA), coated polypropylene suture, a polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) monofilament mesh [DynaMesh© PVDF, 3x15 cm] was and the AbsorbaTack™ absorbable mesh fixation device was used. The AbsorbaTack™ device was produced to provide temporary mesh fixation with retention strength in hernia repairs without leaving behind foreign bodies. It has 4.1-mm long, and 5.1-mm wide proximal wings and absorption is substantially complete before 12 months.

The patients underwent standard preparation before the laparoscopic surgery. Prophylactic antibiotics (2 g of intravenous cefazolin sodium) were administered 30 minutes before surgery, and all the operations were performed under routine standard general anaesthesia [induction: propofol, fentanyl, rocuronium; maintenance: sevoflurane, oxygen and air mixture and remifentanyl infusion). All patients received non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs and tramadol 100 mg intraoperatively as a routine procedure.

The patients were placed in the dorsal lithotomy position, and the left arm was tucked along the patient's side. The skin and vagina were cleaned aseptically using a 10% povidone-iodine solution, and an 18-F catheter was inserted into the bladder. The ring forceps with the sponge was placed into the vagina to manipulate the vaginal cuff and create the optimal position during surgery. The operation time began with the first skin incision and ended when the incision was closed. The trocars and laparoscope were inserted through the abdominal cavity, the 12-mm trocar was inserted into the inferior margin of the umbilicus to introduce the laparoscope, while two 5-mm access ports were placed 2–4 cm medial and inferior to the anterior superior iliac spine on both sides. The pneumoperitoneum was created after 12 mmHg of CO2 insufflation.

Laparoscopic pectopexy technique

In the first step, the peritoneal layer was opened along the left round ligament toward the pelvic side wall. The dissection was continued medially and caudally with a Harmonic scalpel. The left external iliac vessels were identified, and the soft adipose tissue was bluntly dissected caudally to expose the left iliopectineal ligament (Cooper's ligament). A segment of approximately 4 cm was prepared on the iliopectineal ligament for the mesh fixation. The bladder was dissected caudally creating a safe area at the vaginal cuff to place the mesh. The same procedure was

Table 2 Postoperative follow-up results and related surgery measurements

Parameters	Tacker group (n=12) Mean (±SD)	Suture group (n=14) Mean (±SD)	P value
Average of hospital stay (day)	2.3±0.6	2.1±0.4	0.806
Total of analgesic requirement	3.3±0.7	3.7±0.7	0.235
VAS score at 6 h	5.0±2.0	6.0±2.0	0.159
VAS score at 12 h	2.9±1.7	3.6±1.2	0.222
VAS score at 24 h	2.6±1.5	3.4±1.8	0.204
Follow-up period(month)	9.8±5.4	16.4±7.3	0.351
Postoperative 6th-month complication (number of patients)			
Relapse of vaginal apical defect	0	1	-
Voiding difficulties	0	0	-
Dyspareunia	0	0	-
Mesh Erosion	0	0	-
VAS; visual analog scale SD; standart deviation			

applied to the right side. Next, the PVDF monofilament mesh was inserted into the abdominal cavity.

In the suture group, each arm of the mesh was affixed to the respective ipsilateral ligament with two intra-corporeal sutures (Fig. 1A). Also, the middle of the mesh was fixed to the vaginal cuff with four stitches in the tension-free position (Fig. 1B).

In the tacker group, four tacks were used to fixation of mesh to the iliopectineal ligaments (Fig. 2A) and vaginal cuff. (Fig. 2B). Because we know that the 0-polypropylene suture is approximately 2.5 times stronger than the tacks and we made an effort to equalize the fixation strength¹⁷ Finally, the visceral peritoneal defect was closed with continuous sutures (Fig. 3).

The patients were discharged from the hospital when they got normal intestinal and voiding functions, tolerated the oral regimes, got adequate pain relief and performed their normal functions and mobilization. In the postoperative period, we recommended to the patients to use a low dose vaginal estriol treatment and to perform regular pelvic floor exercises to enhance recovery.

Statistical analysis

All the statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows® version 20.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test the normality of the data distribution. The continuous variables were expressed as the mean ± standard deviation, and the categorical variables were expressed as counts (percentages). The comparisons of the normally distributed continuous variables between the groups

Fig.1: The peritoneal layer is opened along the right round ligament toward the pelvic side wall. The peritoneal layers on both sides are opened toward the vaginal cuff. The bladder is dissected caudally, and it is created a safe area on the vaginal cuff to place the mesh. After completion of dissections, a polyvinylidene mesh is inserted into the abdominal cavity. Middle of the mesh is fixed at the vaginal cuff with 4 stitches via polypropylene suture using the intra-corporeal suturing technique.

Fig.2. The ends of the mesh are sutured to both iliopectineal ligaments with 4 tacks via the absorbable mesh fixation devices of commercial tack device - Absorbatack™.

Fig.3. The peritoneal layer is opened along the right round ligament toward the pelvic side wall. The peritoneal layers on both sides are opened toward the vaginal cuff. The bladder is dissected caudally and it is created a safe area on the vaginal cuff to place the mesh. After completion of dissections, a polyvinylidene mesh is inserted into the abdominal cavity. The middle of the mesh is fixed at the vaginal cuff with 4 tacks via the absorbable mesh fixation devices of commercial tack device - Absorbatack™.

were performed using the Independent Samples t-test. The non-normally distributed continuous variables between the groups were evaluated using the Mann-Whitney U test. A two-sided P value <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

In this study, 26 patients underwent laparoscopic pectopexy procedures. Tackers were used for the mesh fixation in 12 operations, and polypropylene sutures were used in 14 operations. Table-1 shows detailed patient demographic parameters.

The time required for the mesh placement was 34.3 ± 5.9 minutes in the suture group and 16.6 ± 3.7 minutes in the tacker group (Table 2, $p < 0.001$). Moreover, the operation time was significantly shorter in the tacker group in comparison with the suture group (Table 2, $p < 0.001$). Our patients exhibited a mean haemoglobin concentration drop of 0.9 g/dl in both groups on the first postoperative day ($p = 0.979$). In the suture group, one patient suffered a bladder injury as a major complication, but no other complications occurred in either group. The VAS scores at 6, 12 and 24 hours did not demonstrate significant differences between the two groups ($p = 0.159$, $p = 0.222$ and $p = 0.215$, respectively). Also, there was no significant difference in the follow-up duration between the two study groups (Table-3, $p = 0.312$). There was one case of apical vaginal prolapse (POP-Q stage II) after the laparoscopic pectopexy in the suture group during the 13-month follow-up period. However, no complaints of voiding difficulties, dyspareunia or low back pain were reported during the follow-up period (Table 2).

Discussion

An optimization technique for vaginal vault repair is associated with a low recurrence rate, low complication rate and high satisfaction rate for both the patients and surgeons. The attachment between the upper third of the vagina (level I), the lateral pelvic walls and the sacrum provides vaginal support, regarding preventing the descent of the vaginal cuff after a hysterectomy [6]. Weak pelvic floor tissues can be supported by mesh fixation with a variety of different surgical techniques, including sacrospinous fixation, sacrocolpopexy [laparoscopic, robotic and abdominal] and laparoscopic pectopex [7,18-19]. Although sacrocolpopexy has been proven to be the gold standard surgical option, a laparoscopic pectopexy is an alternative procedure for treating a vaginal vault prolapse [7,9,18-19].

Absorbable mesh fixation devices have been used successfully in laparoscopic hernia repair for the fixation of prosthetic material to soft tissue, with the goals of decreasing persistent postoperative pain, a high satisfaction rate of the surgeon and shortened operation time [13,16,20]. We believed that fixation of mesh to the iliopectineal ligament via an absorbable tack device might be an alternative method without increasing the complications related to surgery. A previous study comparing the tackers and 0-polypropylene suture showed that the acute fixation strength of the tackers (13.2 ± 3.7 N) was less than that achieved with the polypropylene suture (59.7 ± 7.2 N) in laparoscopic ventral hernia repair [17]. However, in this study, the abdominal wall tissue was used for the mesh fixation. In contrast to the abdominal fascia [21], the iliopectineal ligament is the second strongest ligament in the pelvis [8]. This difference in strength can explain why the mesh fixation via the tackers did not increase the failure rate in the laparoscopic pectopexies when compared to the suture repairs [13]. Our results showed that there was no recurrence in the tackers group; however, there was one vaginal apical prolapse relapse after the laparoscopic pectopexy in the suture group (POP-Q II) during the 13-month follow-up period. This study included a limited number of patients; therefore, it is not possible to say that using tackers was better for preventing vaginal apical prolapse relapses when compared to the suture technique.

In a recent study, Noe et al. fixed the mesh to the iliopectineal ligament with two simple interrupted sutures, and they reported that the average hospital stay was 5.1 days. In our study, the mean hospital stay was 2.3 days in the tackers group and 2.1 days in the suture group, with no significant difference. Although the hospital stay duration was longer in the Noe et al. study, the hospital discharge criteria were not described, and the prolonged hospitalization reasons were not explained [18].

There are plenty of studies investigating the effects of tackers or suture use on the postoperative pain score in hernia repairs. There is one study in which the laparoscopic hernia repairs were carried out with different tack devices did not report any postoperative neuralgia in the patients in the tackers group [13]. Oguz et al. reported that VAS scores on the first postoperative day were significantly lower in the suture patients than the tackers patients undergoing inguinal hernia repairs [12]. Our results confirmed that the tackers group had similar VAS scores when compared to the suture group 6, 12 and 24 hours after the operation ($p = 0.159$, $p = 0.222$ and $p = 0.215$, respectively). The syndrome of pelvic pain after fixation of the vagina to the iliopectineal ligament may result from several causes that involving the reaction of nervous tissue to injury. Intra-ligamentous nerve fibre damage and nerve

entrapments can present as a potential cause of postoperative pain. We are of the opinion that the mesh fixation onto the iliopectineal ligament using a tacker did not produce much more postoperative pain than the mesh fixation with suture. Nevertheless, special care must be taken to avoid injury of the obturator nerve, which is far away from the operating field.

Given the published data, it has been reported that the de novo urinary incontinence rate was 4.8% for patients undergoing pectopexies [9]. However, we detected no voiding difficulties in our patients. No previous studies have investigated the major complication rate, such as bladder, bowel and vessel injuries, in pectopexy surgery. In our study, while the bladder was dissected caudally, the bladder injury as a major intraoperative complication occurred in only one woman in the suture group. The bladder was repaired laparoscopically without conversion to laparotomy. A bladder injury can occur during vaginal cuff preparation, and for that reason, this complication should not be attributed to the suture group.

Similar to other studies, the mean operation duration was shorter in the tacker group [13,17]. Saturation is often technically challenging and time-consuming in laparoscopic surgery. As we expected when designing this study, the mean mesh fixation time was shorter in the tacker group (16.6 minutes in the tacker group versus 34.3 minutes in the suture group).

Even though the absorbable mesh fixation device has not yet been accepted for the mesh pectopexy procedure, routine usage may provide the advantage of a shorter suture time. However, a 20-minute average mesh placement time shortening should discuss the positive effects on decreasing the morbidity rates associated with the anaesthesia risk of the patient. Stapling a mesh via absorbable mesh fixation device onto the vaginal cuff and iliopectineal ligament is faster than it is to suture. Laparoscopic pectopexy surgery is a preferable option for gynaecologists. The strong points of this study; it is the first study that the surgeon performed the laparoscopic pectopexy via absorbable mesh fixation device as an alternative to suture. Second, all procedures were performed by a single surgeon experienced in laparoscopic pectopexy procedures.

The principal limitations of our study, we could not design a prospective randomized controlled trial comparing polypropylene suture versus absorbable tack mesh fixation in laparoscopic pectopexy. This is a retrospective study and has methodological limitations as the patients could not evaluate with questionnaire forms in the preoperatively. Also, the number of participants was small this study evaluated the short-term results.

In our study group, we did not encounter any new risks in the patients who underwent tacker mesh fixations. Also, using an absorbable mesh fixation device can provide a shorter suture time. Absorbable tacker mesh fixation may be a safe, feasible and time-saving alternative to polypropylene suture fixation. However, this study only showed the initial absorbable mesh fixation device experiences in laparoscopic pectopexies. Further prospective comparative studies with more significant numbers of patients are needed to show the long-term results.

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